

Title: A large-scale corpus for assessing source-based writing quality: ASAP 2.0

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Highlights

- We introduce the ASAP 2.0 corpus
- The corpus contains over 25,000 source-based essays
- Each essay is scored for overall writing quality
- The corpus can be used to computationally and quantitatively model source-based writing quality

Introduction

Automatic essay scoring (AES) systems are premised on statistical or machine learning models that can assign scores to essays based on linguistic features within texts that are related to content, structure, and quality of written prose (Shermis & Barrera, 2002; Shermis & Burstein, 2003, Shermis, Burstein, & Leacock, 2006; Yan, Rupp, & Foltz, 2020). AES systems can assist teachers in scoring essays in low-stakes classroom assessments and can offer students greater opportunities for writing practice and feedback (Dikli, 2006; Page, 2003). Additionally, AES systems can benefit large-scale testing services by providing automated and reliable ratings for high-stakes writing assessments. AES systems are often used because scoring essays by hand is resource intensive in terms of norming, scoring, and adjudication (Hunter et al., 1996).

Indeed, government and philanthropic funding agencies have argued that the cost of scoring student writing by hand is unsustainable, calling for greater research into AES systems (Schneider & Garg, 2021). However, AES systems are problematic for a number of reasons related to the simple nature of the writing constructs to which AES systems can attend (i.e., generally surface-level linguistic features, Condon, 2013; Deane, 2013; Haswell, 2006; Haswell & Ericsson, 2006; Herrington & Moran, 2001; Huot, 1996; Perelman, 2012) and the types of writing tasks AES systems can score reliably (i.e., independent writing tasks, Condon, 2013; Elbow & Belanoff, 1986; Wardle & Roozen, 2013).

However, with the advent of large language models (LLMs) and other forms of artificial intelligence, the construct validity and reliability of AES systems should rapidly improve. For instance, the LLMs that power the backend of AES systems examine writing constructs that capture not only traditional features found in the systems, including part of speech tags and

syntactic dependencies but also semantic features such as semantic role labeling, semantic protocols, and semantic relation classification (Tenney, Das, & Pavlick, 2019). Recent research has demonstrated increased reliability in AES systems powered by LLMs. For instance, Holmes et al. (in press) trained two LLMs to automatically assess language proficiency in writing samples as scored by expert raters. Results indicated that the LLMs were as reliable as human raters in that the LLM-human correlations were not significantly different from the human-human correlation. Confirmatory factor analyses indicated excellent alignment between human-generated and model-generated scores as well as a small degree of distinctness between the construct measured by the human raters and the LLMs.

AES systems based on LLMs, however, require large-scale corpora to train, validate, and test models. The corpus that most AES models are trained on is the Automated Student Assessment Prize (ASAP, Shermis, 2014; Shermis & Hamner, 2013) corpus (Li & Ng, 2024). For instance, Yang et al. (2020) developed a state-of-the-art AES system using a pre-trained LLM to learn text representations while simultaneously constraining the scores produced by those representations using machine learning models. Their resulting model outperformed state-of-the-art neural network models in most cases based on quadratic weighted kappa (QWK) reporting an average QWK for the ASAP corpus of .794. However, the ASAP corpus has a number of limitations including a design that does not allow for cross-prompt AES systems because of differences in prompts, scoring, and tasks. Additionally, the corpus contains no demographic or individual data for writers making it difficult to assess bias in scoring models. The corpus also contains transcription errors and does not contain the source-texts for the source-based prompts. Importantly, only the training set is openly available.

Knowing the importance of developing accurate AES systems and understanding the limitations found in the initial ASAP, this paper introduces a corpus of scored essays (ASAP 2.0) that address the concerns found in the original ASAP corpus. ASAP 2.0 builds on ASAP by providing a corpus of ~25,000 scored source-based argumentative essays written by secondary students in the United States on seven different prompts. Essays were written for state-wide testing, and all essays were written using computers. Demographic and individual difference information is available for the majority of writers and each essay was scored on the same 6-scale holistic rubric. Lastly, source texts are available for each prompt. The corpus is open-source and includes a training, validation, and test set. The aim of ASAP 2.0 is to provide a tool that can enhance understanding of persuasive writing and to further the development of unbiased computational algorithms that can estimate overall writing quality. Algorithms derived from the corpus will help guide AES systems to better assess student writing samples and encourage improved revision practices. The insights gained from the corpus will assist researchers and educators in developing classroom strategies to promote proficient writing abilities. The corpus is described in detail in the following sections.

Background

In 2011, the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation (Hewlett) funded the creation of the Automated Student Assessment Prize (ASAP, Shermis, 2014; Shermis & Hamner, 2013). The purpose of ASAP was to explore the effectiveness of machine learning models in assigning quality scores to student writing and how well these scores overlapped with those of trained, human raters. To do so, researchers compiled a corpus of over 22,000 essays written by students and set up two competitions. The first competition invited existing scoring engines to score the essays (a vendor competition), and the second competition was an open competition hosted on

Kaggle that allowed any data scientist to develop essay scoring models. The vendor competition led to a top agreement between humans and models of .78 using QWK while the data scientist competition led to a top agreement of .81 (Shermis & Hamner, 2013). Since then, the corpus of student writing samples found in ASAP has been used hundreds of times to develop new machine-scoring models of human essay quality with recent models highlighting the use of LLMs and generative pretrained transformers (GPTs) to automatically score essays (Mayfield & Black, 2020; Shermis, 2024). However, it is difficult to make comparisons across studies because only the training set for the ASAP essay was made publicly available.

The corpus of essays found in ASAP is problematic in other ways that have limited the results of machine learning models developed on the data. For instance, the data came from six states in the United States that reflected a diversity of state policies, geographics, and demographics. However, while the data is argued to be representative of student populations in terms of ethnic and gender diversity, no information is available for individual student writers. Additionally, the essays were written on eight prompts that came from four different writing tasks: independent persuasive argumentative writing, dependent (source-based) persuasive argumentative writing, expository writing, and narrative writing, limiting generalizations across writing tasks. For the dependent essays, the sources read by the students are not available. Each essay was also scored by two human raters with a final or adjudicated score representing the writing quality of the essay. However, the prompts were scored with different rubrics. Five of the prompts were scored using a holistic scoring rubric that assigned a single quality score to the essay. One prompt employed a two-trait rubric while two prompts were scored with multi-trait rubrics. As a result, essay quality was differentially assigned in ASAP based on prompt, and the scoring scales for each prompt were not aligned ranging from scales of 0-3 to 0-30. Lastly, of the

eight essay sets, six were hand-written requiring the use of digital scanners followed by human checks of the scans and subsequent transcriptions to convert them to digital format. This process likely introduced fidelity errors into the final corpus of essays, as noted by Shermis (2014), including error correction and missing carriage returns and paragraph formatting meta-tags. The inclusion of both hand-written and computer-mediated writing tasks introduces concerns about modeling writing across the prompts because cognitive factors differ based on writing modality (Feng et al., 2019).

ASAP 2.0 Corpus

The goal of this paper is to introduce the ASAP 2.0 corpus, which comprises 24,278 persuasive essays taken from standardized writing tests collected at the state level from 6th, 8th, 9th, and 10th grade students. All essays were sourced-based, requiring students to read and integrate source information into their responses. There were seven prompts in total. Of the ~25,000 essays, 12,871 essays were sourced from the PERSUADE 2.0 corpus (Crossley et al, in press) and 11,829 of the essays have never been released (see Table 1 for descriptives of essays by prompt and grade level). Essays were selected to maximize the amount of demographic information available for each writer including English Language Learning (ELL) status, economic background (disadvantaged or not), disability status, race/ethnicity, gender, and grade level. However, 4,005 essays from the PERSUADE 2.0 corpus did not include information about economic or disability status. An additional 41 essays in the PERSUADE 2.0 corpus did not include ELL status. Of the new essays, 309 did not include ELL status and five did not include race/ethnicity information.

[Insert Table 1 about here]

Economically disadvantaged students were identified based on eligibility for free or reduced-price lunch. Overall, for the essays reporting demographic information, 12,786 essays were written by students classified as economically disadvantaged and 7,937 essays were written by students classified as not disadvantaged. Student disability was categorized based on status of the student having an individualized education plan (IEP) or 504 plan. Within the ASAP 2.0 corpus, 2,977 essays were written by students with disabilities and 17,746 essays were written by students without disabilities. ELL status was provided by the data sources. In total, 3,276 essays written by ELL students and 21,010 were not. The essays were generally evenly split between male (n = 12,516) and female (n = 12,12) writers. In terms of race/ethnicity, the majority of essays were written by White students (n = 9,867) followed by Hispanic students (n = 7,183), Black/African-American students (n = 4,588), students with two or more races (n = 1,525) and Asian/Pacific Islander students (n = 1,417). A small number of essays were written by American Indian/Alaskan Native students (n = 144).

Each essay was scored holistically using a standardized rubric. The rubric was a modified Scholastic Aptitude Test (SAT) rubric developed specifically for source-based writing (see Appendix A). The rubric used a 1 to 6 scale that had interval levels with a score of 6 indicating consistent mastery of writing. Mastery in writing was indicated by an effective point of view, outstanding critical thinking, the use of clear examples and reasons, and appropriate evidence from sources. Linguistically, high-scored essays showed strong organization and cohesion as well as the skillful use of language including vocabulary, sentence structure, and grammar and mechanics.

The ~13,000 PERSUADE 2.0 essays were scored by 20 expert raters employed by an outside consulting firm using a double-blind rating process followed by 100 percent

adjudication. Inter-rater reliability before adjudication indicated strong agreement between the expert raters (weighted $\kappa = .745$, $r = .750$). Raters also flagged essays for personal identifying information (PII), which was later removed. The additional ~12,000 essays that rounded out the ASAP 2.0 corpus were also scored by 14 expert raters from an outside consulting firm. These raters also flagged essays that contained PII. Inter-rater reliability before adjudication indicated acceptable agreement between the expert raters (weighted $\kappa = .659$, $r = .750$). All 34 raters took anti-bias strategy instruction and anti-bias training prior to rating. The training highlighted issues of bias that can occur during essay annotation that are an inherent part of standardized rubrics (Warner, 2018). All 34 raters were trained by prompt and then scored essays on that prompt individually.

The corpus is freely available at anonymous.github.com. The GitHub repositories include the training data and access to the test data (through a password protected zip file). The corpus is formatted as a dataframe that uses comma-separated values for structure. The dataframe includes 13 columns for each essay including an anonymous identification number, the average human assigned score for the essay, the full text for the essay, and the essay prompt and assignment. Source texts are provided in a separate folder. Additionally, where available, there are columns for each essay that provide information about the economic status, disability status, ELL status, gender, grade level, and race/ethnicity of the writer. Lastly, there are two columns that provide information about the division of the dataset into training and test sets for the Kaggle competition. The first column indicates whether the essay was in the training or the test set. If the essay was in the test set, a second column indicates whether it was part of the validation set (public) or the withheld test set (private).

Possible Futures

Like the original ASAP, the ASAP 2.0 corpus was used in a public competition hosted by Kaggle in 2024. Around 70% of the corpus was released publicly on Kaggle and 30% was kept hidden as a test set. Kaggle data scientists only had access to the essays and the human scores assigned to the essays. The data scientists did not have access to prompt information nor student economic status, disability status, ELL status, race/ethnicity, grade level, or gender. The competition tasked participants to train a model to automatically score student essays (i.e., develop an AES model). The training and test sets (including the validation set within the test set) were stratified by score, prompt, and demographic information to ensure a balance across the sets. Competition success was measured using a quadratic weighted Kappa score, making the results comparable with the original ASAP prize. To incentivize participation, \$55,000 in prize money was offered to winning submissions, with the money evenly split between a normal competition and an efficiency prize that rewarded data scientists for creating simpler models that were not computationally heavy. The goal was to produce more complex models using AI and simpler models which would have a lower carbon footprint and be easier to integrate into real-world educational contexts where computational capabilities may be limited. A main difference between the two competitions was the main prize models had access to a GPU while the efficiency prize models could only access a CPU.

Over 2,500 teams and almost 3,500 competitors participated in the ASAP 2.0 competition. In total, they developed over 60,000 AES models. The winning models from the main prize reported accuracies of around 84%. All winning models were dependent on large language models to assess writing quality. The winning models from the efficiency prize reported accuracies of around 82% and depended on more classic natural language processing features such as number of words, key words, and part of speech (POS) tags.

While the entire ASAP 2.0 corpus was not initially available in the Kaggle competition, the corpus has been released under a Creative Commons license international license. Our goal in releasing the full dataset is to advance AES research so that new models can be developed on a robust corpus of source-based writing samples that have a common scoring metric and similar tasks and expectations. The size of the dataset along with the reliability of the human scores should allow for stronger models of writing quality to be developed that can help teachers with grading tasks and provide students with summarized feedback. Additionally, the release of demographic and individual difference measures should allow researchers to assess bias in any models developed, which is particularly important for AES systems developed using large language models (Balfour et al., 2022).

The main goal of ASAP 2.0 is for the development of improved AES systems, especially models developed on more than just surface-level features (Perelman, 2012). With the advent of LLMs, the assessment of essay quality at the level of semantics and discourse is now possible (Mayfield & Black, 2020; Shermis, 2024; Yang et al., 2020). AES systems based on LLMs should lead to more consistent, objective, and efficient scoring that increases reliability. These systems can also alleviate concerns related to the subjectivity and inconsistency found in human raters including the same rater assigning different scores to the same essay at different times and normed raters not reaching agreement on essay scores (Ling et al., 2014; Williamson et al., 1999). AES systems that can score essays in a manner consistent with human raters would allow students greater opportunities to write essays, receive summative feedback, and revise. This is especially true because the time and effort needed for humans to evaluate essays individually is prohibitive, delaying opportunities for feedback. LLM-powered AES systems would also help

reduce the costs and time associated with essay scoring and conserve resources for government and industry.

One problem with traditional AES systems is that they provide summative and not formative feedback, which is the type of feedback that is important for students during the revising process. Thus, while AES systems can assign essay quality scores, they are not capable of explaining why the score was assigned. AES systems developed using ASAP 2.0 would have a few advantages over other scored corpora because over half of the ASAP 2.0 essays come from the PERSUADE corpus, which provides segmental annotations for the presence and quality of discourse elements like final claims, evidence, and rebuttals. Essay quality scores in ASAP 2.0 could be explained by the presence of discourse elements allowing for the development of more complex automatic writing evaluation (AWE) systems to provide both summative and formative to students. Additionally, the size of ASAP and the controlled nature of the corpus would allow for the development of linguistic-based components of essays related to essay quality that might help explain AES systems' judgments. For instance, a principal component analysis could be used to develop latent writing components related to cohesion, grammar/mechanics, vocabulary use, or syntactic complexity. These components could then be correlated with essay scores to enhance AES system feedback to students about potential features in essays that are driving scoring (cf., Crossley et al., 2014a, 2014b).

Connections

Since ASAP 2.0 builds on the original ASAP database, we expect strong connections can be made between the two corpora. At a low level, ASAP 2.0 can be used to assess the generalizability of previous AES models developed on the original ASAP database. Testing the generalizability of these models is not limited simply to how those models can reliably score

essays in ASAP 2.0, but also to how well the models avoid bias in scoring in reference to demographic and individual differences. More importantly, ASAP 2.0 data along with the original ASAP data could be used to develop cross-prompt models that are trained on numerous prompts instead of a single prompt, making resulting AES systems more scalable. For instance, the original ASAP dataset contained four source-based prompts that could be used to extend cross-prompt models, although the human ratings would have to be scaled between the two datasets to enable comparisons.

Connections could also be made between the ASAP 2.0 dataset and other existing scored writing corpora to assess differences in human ratings for different writing tasks including independent, summarizations, narrative, and expository writing samples and for different populations based on grade levels, English language learner status, prompt, and scoring rubric. For instance, ASAP 2.0 could be paired with the TOEFL 11 dataset, which is a collection of 11,000 TOEFL-independent writing samples from 11 different first-language backgrounds that have labels for low, medium, and high proficiency (Blanchard et al., 2013). Combining ASAP 2.0 with TOEFL 11 could be helpful in developing models of writing quality scaled to include adult second language (L2) writers. Incorporating essays from the English Language Learner Insight, Proficiency and Skills Evaluation (ELLIPSE, Crossley et al., 2023) Corpus, the Cambridge Learner Corpus-First Certificate in English exam (CLCFCE, Yannakoudakis et al., 2011), and the International Corpus of Learner English (ICLE, Granger et al., 2009) could help develop generalizable models of writing that attend to L2 writers as well as L1 writers of all ages and backgrounds. In general, combining ASAP 2.0 with other essay datasets would provide researchers with opportunities to better understand writing expectations across a wide breadth of tasks, populations, and expectations.

Limitations

The ASAP 2.0 corpus expands on the initial ASAP corpus and addresses many of its limitations related to demographic and individual difference information, scoring metrics, prompts, writing tasks, and writing modality. However, ASAP 2.0 is not without its own limitations. For example, the corpus has a small number of prompts ($N = 7$) and only focuses on students from 6th to 10th grade in the United States. All AES models developed only on the ASAP 2.0 corpus may not generalize to older or younger students or to additional prompts (although LLMs can include prompt information during modeling which may allow for greater generalizability). Another limitation is that the ASAP 2.0 corpus only includes dependent essays and does not include essays from other writing tasks such as independent, narrative, or expository writing. This decision was purposeful because most classroom writing is source-based, and almost all standardized assessments of writing now include dependent writing prompts to mirror real-world writing tasks. Additionally, as noted, the ASAP 2.0 corpus may work best when connected with existing corpora that make up for these potential limitations. Lastly, while ASAP 2.0 provides much information about the writers' backgrounds, a sizeable number of essays do not have corresponding information about economic or disability status. This may limit, to a degree, checks for bias in AES models derived from the dataset.

References

- Baffour, P., Saxberg, T., & Crossley, S. (2023). Analyzing Bias in Large Language Model Solutions for Assisted Writing Feedback Tools: Lessons from the Feedback Prize Competition Series. *In Proceedings of the 2023 BEA 18th Workshop on Innovative Use of NLP for Building Educational Applications*. (pp. 242–246).
- Blanchard, D., Tetreault, J., Higgins, D., Cahill, A., & Chodorow, M. (2013). TOEFL11: A corpus of non-native English. *ETS Research Report Series*, 2013(2):i–15.
- Condon, W. (2013). Large-scale assessment, locally-developed measures, and automated scoring of essays: Fishing for red herrings? *Assessing Writing*, 18, 100–108.
- Crossley, S. A., Allen, L., & McNamara, D. S. (2014). A multidimensional analysis of essay writing: What linguistic features tell us about situational parameters and the effects of language functions on judgments of quality. In T. B. Sardinha and M. V. Pinto (Eds.), *Multi-Dimensional Analysis, 25 years on: A Tribute to Douglas Biber*. (pp. 197-238). Philadelphia, PA: John Benjamins.
- Crossley, S. A., Baffour, P., Tian, Y., Franklin, A., Benner, M., & Boser., U. (2024). A large-scale corpus for assessing written argumentation: PERSUADE 2.0. *Assessing Writing*, 61.
- Crossley, S. A., Tian, Y., Baffour, P., Franklin, A., Kim, Y., Morris, W., Benner, B., Picou, A., & Boser, U. (2023). Measuring second language proficiency using the English Language Learner Insight, Proficiency and Skills Evaluation (ELLIPSE) Corpus. *International Journal of Learner Corpus Research*, 9 (2), 248-269.
- Crossley, S. A., & McNamara, D. S. (2014). Developing Component Scores from Natural Language Processing Tools to Assess Human Ratings of Essay Quality. In Eberle, W., &

- Boonthum-Denecke, C. (Eds.). *Proceedings of the 27th International Florida Artificial Intelligence Research Society (FLAIRS) Conference*. (pp. 381-386). Menlo Park, CA: The AAAI Press.
- Deane, P. (2013). On the relation between automated essay scoring and modern views of the writing construct. *Assessing Writing, 18*, 7–24.
- Dikli, S. (2006). An overview of automated scoring of essays. *Journal of Technology, Learning, and Assessment, 5*.
- Elbow, P., & Belanoff, P. (1986). Using portfolios to judge writing proficiency at SUNY Stony Brook. In: P. Connolly & T. Vilardi (Eds.), *New directions in college writing programs* (pp. 95–105). New York, NY: Modern Language Association.
- Feng, L., Lindner, A., Ji, X. R., & Malatesha Joshi, R. (2019). The roles of handwriting and keyboarding in writing: A meta-analytic review. *Reading and Writing, 32*, 33-63.
- Granger, S., Dagneaux, E., Meunier, F., & Paquot, M. (2009). *International Corpus of Learner English (Version 2)*. Presses universitaires de Louvain.
- Haswell, R. H. (2006). Automatons and automated scoring: Drudges, black boxes, and dei ex machina. In: P. F. Ericsson & R. H. Haswell (Eds.), *Machine scoring of student essays: Truth and consequences* (pp. 57–78). Logan, UT: Utah State University Press.
- Haswell, R., & Ericsson, P. (Eds.). (2006). *Machine scoring of student essays: Truth and consequences*. Logan, UT: Utah State University Press.
- Herrington, A., & Moran, C. (2001). What happens when machines read our students' writing? *College English, 63*, 480–499.

- Holmes, L., Morris, W., Crossley, S. A., & Choi, J. S. (in press). Assessing the Reliability and Concurrent Validity of Transformer-based Language Proficiency Scores. *Language Testing*.
- Huot, B. (1996). Towards a new theory of writing assessment. *College Composition and Communication*, 47, 549–566.
- Hunter, D. M., Jones, R. M., & Randhawa, B. S. (1996). The use of holistic versus analytic scoring for large-scale assessment of writing. *The Canadian Journal of Program Evaluation*, 11(2), 61–85.
- Li, S., & Ng, V. (2024). Automated essay scoring: Recent successes and future directions. *In Proceedings of the 33rd International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, Jeju, Republic of Korea.
- Ling, G., Mollaun P., Xi, X. A study on the impact of fatigue on human raters when scoring speaking responses. *Language Testing* 31(4), 479-499 (2014).
- Mayfield, E., & Black, A. W. (2020, July). Should you fine-tune BERT for automated essay scoring?. *In Proceedings of the Fifteenth Workshop on Innovative Use of NLP for Building Educational Applications* (pp. 151-162).
- Page, E. B. (3002). Project Essay Grade: PEG. In M. D. Shermis & J. Burstein (Eds.), *Automated essay scoring: A cross-disciplinary perspective* (pp. 43-54). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Perelman, L. (2012). Construct validity, length, score, and time in holistically graded writing assessments: The case against automated essay scoring (AES). In: C. Bazerman, C. Dean, J. Early, K. Lunsford, S. Null, P. Rogers, & A. Stansell (Eds.), *International advances in*

- writing research: Cultures, places, measures* (pp. 121–131). Fort Collins, Colorado: WAC Clearinghouse/Anderson, SC: Parlor Press.
- Schneider, M., & Garg, K. (2021). We need a SpaceX for assessment. *The Hechinger Report*.
<https://hechingerreport.org/opinion-we-need-a-spacex-for-assessment/>
- Shermis, M. D. (2014). State-of-the-art automated essay scoring: Competition, results, and future directions from a United States demonstration. *Assessing Writing*, 20, 53-76.
- Shermis, M. D. (2024). Using ChatGPT to Score Essays and Short-Form Constructed Responses. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.09540*.
- Shermis, M. D., & Barrera, F. D. (2002). Automated essay scoring for electronic portfolios. *Assessment Update*, 14(4), 1-2.
- Shermis, M. D., & Burstein, J. (2003). *Automated essay scoring: A cross-disciplinary perspective*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- Shermis, M. D., Burstein, J., & Leacock, C. (2006). Applications of computers in assessment and analysis of writing. In C. A. McArthur, S. Graham, & J. Fitzgerald (Eds.), *Handbook of writing research* (pp. 403-416). New York, NY: Guilford Press
- Shermis, M. D., & Morgan, J. (2015). Using prizes to facilitate change in educational assessment. In *Technology and Testing* (pp. 323-338). Routledge.
- Shermis, M. D., & Hamner, B. (2013). Contrasting state-of-the-art automated scoring of essays. In *Handbook of automated essay evaluation* (pp. 313-346). Routledge.
- Tenney, I. (2019). BERT rediscovers the classical NLP pipeline. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1905.05950*.
- Wardle, E., & Roozen, K. (2013). Addressing the complexity of writing development: Toward an ecological model of assessment. *Assessing Writing*, 17, 106–119.

- Warner, J. (2018). *Why they can't write: Killing the five-paragraph essay and other necessities*. JHU Press.
- Williamson, D. M., Bejar, I. I., & Hone, A. S. (1999). Mental model comparison of automated and human scoring. *Journal of Educational Measurement*, 36(2), 158–184.
- Yan, D., Rupp, A. A., & Foltz, P. W. (Eds.). (2020). *Handbook of automated scoring: Theory into practice*. London, UK: Chapman and Hall/CRC.
- Yang, R., Cao, J., Wen, Z., Wu, Y., & He, X. (2020, November). Enhancing automated essay scoring performance via fine-tuning pre-trained language models with combination of regression and ranking. *In Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2020* (pp. 1560-1569).
- Yannakoudakis, H., Briscoe, T., & Medlock, B. (2011). A new dataset and method for automatically grading ESOL texts. *In Proceedings of the 49th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, 180–189*, Portland, Oregon, USA. Association for Computational Linguistics.

Table 1

Prompt and grade level descriptives

Prompt	Grade level	n
A Cowboy Who Rode the Waves	6	2175
The Face on Mars	8	3015
The electoral college	9	2046
Car-free cities	10	1959
Driverless cars	10	6170
Exploring Venus	10	4480
Facial action coding system	10	4883

Appendix A

Holistic Rating Form

After reading each essay and completing the analytical rating form, assign a holistic score based on the rubric below. For the following evaluations you will need to use a grading scale between 1 (minimum) and 6 (maximum). As with the analytical rating form, the distance between each grade (e.g., 1-2, 3-4, 4-5) should be considered equal.

SCORE OF 6: An essay in this category **demonstrates clear and consistent mastery**, although it may have a few minor errors. A typical essay effectively and insightfully develops a point of view on the issue and demonstrates outstanding critical thinking; *the* essay uses clearly appropriate examples, reasons, and other evidence *taken from the source text(s)* to support its position; the essay is well organized and clearly focused, demonstrating clear coherence and smooth progression of ideas; the essay exhibits skillful use of language, using a varied, accurate, and apt vocabulary and demonstrates meaningful variety in sentence structure; the essay is free of most errors in grammar, usage, and mechanics.

SCORE OF 5: An essay in this category **demonstrates reasonably consistent mastery**, although it will have occasional errors or lapses in quality. A typical essay effectively develops a point of view on the issue and demonstrates strong critical thinking; *the essay* generally using appropriate examples, reasons, and other evidence *taken from the source text(s)* to support its position; the essay is well organized and focused, demonstrating coherence and progression of ideas; the essay exhibits facility in the use of language, using appropriate vocabulary demonstrates variety in sentence structure; the essay is generally free of most errors in grammar, usage, and mechanics.

SCORE OF 4: An essay in this category **demonstrates adequate mastery**, although it will have lapses in quality. A typical essay develops a point of view on the issue and demonstrates competent critical thinking; *the essay* using adequate examples, reasons, and other evidence *taken from the source text(s)* to support its position; the essay is generally organized and focused, demonstrating some coherence and progression of ideas exhibits adequate; the essay may demonstrate inconsistent facility in the use of language, using generally appropriate vocabulary demonstrates some variety in sentence structure; the essay may have some errors in grammar, usage, and mechanics.

SCORE OF 3: An essay in this category **demonstrates developing mastery**, and is marked by ONE OR MORE of the following weaknesses: develops a point of view on the issue, demonstrating some critical thinking, but may do so inconsistently or use inadequate examples, reasons, or other evidence *taken from the source texts* to support its position; the essay is limited in its organization or focus, or may demonstrate some lapses in coherence or progression of ideas displays; the essay may demonstrate facility in the use of language, but sometimes uses weak vocabulary or inappropriate word choice and/or lacks variety or demonstrates problems in sentence structure; the essay may contain an accumulation of errors in grammar, usage, and mechanics.

SCORE OF 2: An essay in this category **demonstrates little mastery**, and is flawed by ONE OR MORE of the following weaknesses: develops a point of view on the issue that is vague or seriously limited, and demonstrates weak critical thinking; *the essay provides* inappropriate or insufficient examples, reasons, or other evidence *taken from the source text* to support its position; the essay is poorly organized and/or focused, or demonstrates serious problems with coherence or progression of ideas; the essay displays very little facility in the use of language, using very limited vocabulary or incorrect word choice and/or demonstrates frequent problems in sentence structure; the essay contains errors in grammar, usage, and mechanics so serious that meaning is somewhat obscured.

SCORE OF 1: An essay in this category **demonstrates very little or no mastery**, and is severely flawed by ONE OR MORE of the following weaknesses: develops no viable point of view on the issue, or provides little or no evidence to support its position; the essay is disorganized or unfocused, resulting in a disjointed or incoherent essay; the essay displays fundamental errors in vocabulary and/or demonstrates severe flaws in sentence structure; the essay contains pervasive errors in grammar, usage, or mechanics that persistently interfere with meaning.